

Table for the manuscript: Patterns of acute kidney injury in high-income countries

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Table. Comparison of AKI characteristics and outcomes in representative studies performed in high-income countries

AKI type	Population age, years	Males	AKI stages, %			Mortality in AKI patients, %	Kidney function recovery, %
			1	2	3		
Studies evaluating mortality and recovery on day 7*							
Italy (Cappadona et al.)							
CA-HM, HA	69.2±17.7	50%	59.5%	25.7%	14.8%	17.6%	82.4% recovered 17.6% not recovered
Scotland (Wang et al.)							
CA-CM, CA-HM, HA	75 [63–83]	45%	80%	13%	7%	8.6%	35.2% recovered 33.0% not recovered 23.1% not tested
CA-CM	69 [52–80]	35%	89%	8%	3%	1.8%	10.4% recovered 21.0% not recovered 66.7% not tested
CA-HM	74 [63–83]	50%	68%	19%	13%	11.0%	47.0% recovered 33.3% not recovered 8.7% not tested
HA	78 [67–85]	47%	86%	10%	4%	10.4%	38.4% recovered 40.4% not recovered 10.7% not tested
Studies evaluating mortality and recovery on day 30							
Canada (Sawhney et al.) §							
CA-HM, HA	59.6	46.7%	70.1%	18.0%	11.9%	13.1%	65.0% recovered 35.0% not recovered
Denmark (Sawhney et al.) §							
CA-HM, HA	65.0	48.0%	66.2%	19.1%	14.6%	16.5%	67.8% recovered 32.2% not recovered
UK (Sawhney et al.) §							
CA-HM, HA	66.3	45.9%	69.1%	19.0%	11.9%	15.8%	69.7% recovered 30.3% not recovered
UK national report ‡							
CA-CM	68.4	42.4%	84.2%	9.6%	6.2%	-	-
CA-HM	73.8	52.1%	56.2%	22.7%	21.1%	19.0%	-
HA	76.3	49.7%	73.5%	16.2%	10.3%	23.0%	-

AKI – acute kidney injury; CA-CM – community-acquired AKI managed in community; CA-HM – community-acquired AKI managed in hospital; HA – hospital-acquired AKI.

* For Cappadona et al. the hospitalisation duration was 7 (IQR 4–13) days, for Wang et al the outcomes are measured exactly on day 7. § Recovery status on day 90, percentage

calculated approximately as mean over the observed period; data from all reported years are recalculated to have a single estimate for a country; median age is reported. ‡ Peak AKI stage is considered for stages allocation.